

Building the Legal Knowledge Graph for Smart Compliance Services in Multilingual Europe

D4.5 Final implementation and report of Data and Content Curation Services

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ACRONYMS LIST

BB	Building Block
BPMN	Business Process Model and Notation
CWM	Curation Workflow Manager
DAG	Directed Acyclic Graph
DCM	Document Manager
DS	Dataset
EntEx	Entity Extraction
GEO	Geolocation information extraction
GUI	Graphical User Interface
LKG	Legal Knowledge Graph
NER	Named Entity Recognition
RDF	Resource Description Framework
RelEx	Relation Extraction
RFP	Request for Proposal
SC	Scenario
SeSim	Semantic Similarity
StrEx	Document Structure Analysis
Summ	Summarization
TERM	Terminology extraction
TIMEX	Temporal Expression Analysis
ToClass	Topic Classification (Detection)
TRANS	Translation
UC	Use Case
URI	Uniform Resource Identifier
WM	Workflow Manager
WME	Workflow Manager Engine
WP	Work Package
WSD	Word Sense Disambiguation

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This report describes the final implementation of the curation workflow manager (WM), which controls the workflows associated to every business use case (as defined in *“D4.1 Pilots requirements analysis report”* [LynxD41]). This implementation is based on the definition provided in *“D4.2 Initial version of Workflow definition”* [LynxD42] and *“D4.3 Final version of Workflow definition”* [LynxD43], in which we outlined four workflows: a common workflow, LKG population, and three use case specific workflows, namely Contract Analysis (OLS), Geothermal Project Analysis (DNVGL), and Labour Law Analysis (CuatreCasas), and *“D4.4 Initial implementation and report of Data and Content Curation Services”* [LynxD44] where an initial implementation was described.

The final implementation of the curation workflow manager is based on the Camunda BPMN engine (<https://camunda.com/products/bpmn-engine/>), allowing the definition, implementation and execution of workflows inside the same Lynx platform. The main components of the curation workflow manager were already described in *“D4.4 Initial implementation and report of Data and Content Curation Services”* [LynxD44].

This report also describes the final implementation of the document manager (DCM), which is responsible for the storage of the Legal Knowledge Graph and the documents once they have been processed through the different workflows. One implementation of the DCM is based on Trellis Linked Data Platform (LDP) (<https://www.trellisldp.org/>). A second implementation is based on ElasticSearch (ES). By utilizing the flexibility of JSON-LD and the capabilities of an LDP, the DCM is the main building component for storing the Lynx Legal Knowledge Graph (LKG).

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1 INTRODUCTION

Since the Lynx platform has been designed using a microservice architecture, a curation workflow manager (CWM) is needed in order to orchestrate all the different services. This manager is responsible for the execution of all workflows defined in Lynx, therefore it must be able to contact all the services, named Building Blocks (BB) in Work Package 3 (WP3), and datasets in order to implement the required functionality. The datasets are stored by the document manager (DCM), which is responsible for the storage of the Legal Knowledge Graph (LKG) and the enriched documents that are processed through the workflows.

The document manager is implemented in a flexible manner using two different data storages: Elastic Search (ES) and the Trellis Linked Data Platform (LDP). By utilizing the flexibility of JSON-LD and the capabilities of an LDP, the DCM is the main building component of the Lynx Legal Knowledge Graph (LKG) and where the LKG is stored. Further information on the Legal Knowledge Graph can be found in the devoted section of *“D2.4 Data Management Plan”* [LynxD24].

A complete description of the Workflow Manager and the Document Manager can be found in *“D4.4 Initial implementation and report of Data and Content Curation Services”* [LynxD44].

Finally we have implemented three of the four workflows defined in *“D4.3 Final version of Workflow definition”* [LynxD43]:

- Legal Knowledge Graph Population
- Contract Analysis
- Geothermal Project Analysis

The last workflow defined in *“D4.3”*, Labour Law Analysis, has been implemented independently because it is more focused on Information Retrieval as in Document Analysis.

1.1 PURPOSE OF THIS DOCUMENT

This report describes the final implementation of the curation workflow manager and the document manager as components of the Lynx platform. The document is based on *D4.4 Initial implementation and report of Data and Content Curation Services* [LynxD44], which defines the initial implementation of the workflow manager, and *D4.3 Final version of Workflow definition* [LynxD43], which defines the final version of the workflows, and aligned with *D1.1 Functional requirements analysis report* [LynxD11] and *D4.1 Pilots requirements analysis report* [LynxD41], which define the requirements for the Lynx platform collected from the use case pilots.

1.2 STRUCTURE OF THIS DOCUMENT

The rest of this deliverable is organized as follows:

- Section 2 [Document Manager](#) describes the document manager which handles the stored information inside the platform.
- Section 3 [Curation Workflow Manager](#) describes the curation workflow manager as a component of the Lynx platform and the four implemented workflows.
- Section 4 [Conclusions](#) concludes this deliverable.
- Annex 1 presents details of the code repositories.
- Annex 2 and Annex3 consist of the openAPI description of the DCM and CWM HTTP endpoints.

2 DOCUMENT MANAGER

The Document Manager (DCM) is an integral part of the Lynx Platform. This is where all documents are stored after the successful execution of the enrichment workflows and maintained. It provides read/write access to internal services (mainly the Workflow Manager) and to the end user applications. The basic architecture and the main functionalities of the DCM (see [Figure 1](#)) have been described on “D4.1 Pilots requirements analysis report” [LynxD41]. An extension covering the updates on the annotations controller has been provided on “D4.4 Initial implementation and report of Data and Content Curation Services” [LynxD44]. In this deliverable we will report on the new validation controller, and the basic search functionality offered by the DCM. The complete documentation of the API can be found in ANNEX 3 and an interactive version of it on <https://lynx-project.eu/doc/api/>.¹

We will also summarize the LKG in the DCM.

Figure 1. High-level Architecture of the Document Manager

2.1 VALIDATION CONTROLLER

The Lynx shared data models currently used by many microservices are described in “D2.4 Data Management Plan”. To support the validation of RDF graphs against the rules established by the Lynx Data Model, two SHACL shapes have been defined, one for the NIF 2.1 ontology and one for the Lynx ontology. [Table 1](#) includes links to these three resources. In order to maintain data and system integrity, all inputs to the Document Manager should be valid Lynx Documents according to the specified data model.

¹ <https://lynx-project.eu/doc/api/lynx-swagger-ui.html?openapi-server-url=https://apis.lynx-project.eu/doc/open-api-3/document-manager>

Resource	Description	URL
Lynx Ontology	The Lynx Ontology, used to describe the Lynx Documents	https://lynx-project.eu/doc/lkg.ttl
NIF 2.1 SHACL shapes	SHACL shapes used to validate part of the NIF2.1 ontology.	https://lynx-project.eu/doc/nif-shapes.ttl
Lynx SHACL shapes	SHACL shapes used to validate documents based on the specification of the Lynx Data Model - https://lynx-project.eu/doc/lkg/	https://lynx-project.eu/doc/lynx-shapes.ttl

Table 1. Lynx Data Model Resources

The validation service is able to validate documents according to the Lynx Data Model. The TopBraid SHACL API is used internally as the SHACL engine to perform constraint checking. Besides the default shapes, custom validation modules can be set up and used on the validation process. This feature covers the need for use case specific rules as emerged from the pilots implementations.

The validation service accepts input in various RDF serializations. The response is a JSON object providing the following elements (see [Figure 2](#)):

- valid: A Boolean value, true if the document is valid, false otherwise.
- reports: The validation reports serialized as JSON objects. The validation report is described with the SHACL Validation Report Vocabulary as defined by the official specification (<https://www.w3.org/TR/shacl/#validation-report>). This vocabulary defines the RDF properties to represent structural information that may provide guidance on how to identify or fix violations in the data graph.
- Status: HTTP status of the request

```

{
  "valid":false,
  "reports":[
    {
      "title":"NIF 2.1 Validation Report",
      "results":[]
    },
    {
      "title":"LYNX Data Model Validation Report",
      "results":[
        {
          "focusNode":"0e251471123bc3422973d104548cf290",
          "message":"006 - There can be at most one jurisdiction",
          "path":"http://data.europa.eu/eli/ontology#jurisdiction",
          "severity":"http://www.w3.org/ns/shacl#Violation",
          "sourceConstraint":null,
          "sourceShape":"786cf37c9bf3a65dd0985116bafcd63",
          "value":"NLE"
        },
        {"focusNode": "https://apis.lynx-project.eu/document-platform"},
        {"focusNode": "https://apis.lynx-project.eu/document-platform"}
      ]
    }
  ],
  "status":200
}
    
```

Figure 2. A sample validation report message

2.2 BASIC SEARCH

As an alternative to the Advanced Search service (SEAR), described in “D3.9 Information Retrieval and Recommender Services” [LynxD39], the document manager now offers an endpoint to perform basic search functionalities. Queries on this endpoint are mapped into SPARQL query templates. Full-text search on the contents of a document is available. The GET call (shown in [Figure 3](#)) accepts the following parameters:

- collectionId: (String) to specify the collection of documents
- query: (String) the text query to perform
- limit: (integer) limiting the number of results
- offset: (integer) causes the results generated to start after the specified number of results. Used for basic pagination

The screenshot shows a web interface for the Basic Search API. At the top, it displays the HTTP method 'GET' and the endpoint path '/collections/{collectionId}/documents/search' with a note 'Makes a search'. Below this is a 'Parameters' section with a 'Try it out' button. The parameters are listed in a table-like format:

Name	Description
collectionId * required string (path)	collectionId
query array[string] (query)	
limit integer (query)	Default value : 10 10
offset integer (query)	Default value : 0 offset

Figure 3. The Basic Search API

2.3 LEGAL KNOWLEDGE GRAPH IN THE DOCUMENT MANAGER

Whereas the Legal Knowledge Graph is extensively described in “D2.4 Data Management Plan”, further updated in “D2.8 Final report of the data management activities”, this section describes the Legal Knowledge Graph (LKG) from the perspective of the Data Curation Workflows.

Definition of the LKG. One of the main results of the Lynx project has been the **definition** of a Legal Knowledge Graph “of legal and regulatory data towards compliance, in which heterogeneous data sources from different jurisdictions, languages and orders are aggregated and interlinked by a collection of advanced services”. This broad definition doesn’t specify where data lives (within or out of Lynx servers) nor the nature of elements in the graph, nor their relation with the curation workflows.

Location of the entities. The Knowledge Graphs represented as RDF in the web have a singular nature: they are unbounded. In the Linked Data Cloud, entities in one server are connected to entities in other server, in turn connected to others and so on. There is no clear cut on what can be of interest --hence the Legal Knowledge Graph, in the broader sense, spans the entire online space. However, some of the entities are key for the Lynx platform to exist --hence some of the entities are served by Lynx servers.

[Figure 4](#) represents legal entities as RDF within the blue box. They are connected to other RDF entities of interest for the legal domain hosted somewhere else, and connected to even some non-RDF documents.

Figure 4. The Legal Knowledge Graph within and out of the Lynx domain

Types of entities within the Lynx Legal Knowledge Graph.

Limited to the entities served by the Lynx servers, [Figure 5](#) depicts the different types of entities that are represented, which are mainly documents (grey boxes) -LynxDocuments, comprising standards, acts, directives, etc.-, concepts and terminological information in concept schemes (white boxes) and other less relevant entities such as organizations and companies.

Figure 5. Types of entities in the Legal LKG

LynxDocuments are by large the most important type of entity in the LKG. They are not a mere transformation of existing data published by the EU official institutions. Instead, they have been enriched by the curation workflows described in this deliverable (see [Figure 6](#)). The next section describes how these elements have been enriched.

Figure 6. Enrichment Process of Lynx Documents

3 CURATION WORKFLOW MANAGER

Using a microservice architecture enforces the usage of some kind of management in order to orchestrate its components to fulfill the expected functionalities.

3.1 WORKFLOW MANAGER ENGINE

Figure 7 depicts the internal architecture of the Workflow Manager, which has not undergone significant changes from what has been presented in “D4.4 Initial implementation and report of Data and Content Curation Services” [LynxD44].

Figure 7. Architecture of the Workflow Manager

As shown in the figure, the main components of the Workflow Manager are:

- Workflow Manager engine: it is responsible for coordinating the execution of tasks in the order specified by a workflow, which is represented using a Business Process Model and Notation (BPMN) diagram. When a new task is available, the Workflow Manager engine “publishes” it in a queue to be fetched and executed by a task executor.
- Task executors²: they are responsible for the execution of tasks published by the Workflow Manager engine. Every task is associated with a type of microservice (e.g. “NER”, “TimEx” ...). Every task executor is also associated with a specific type, and it can process only tasks of its type. Task executors can be easily scaled in and out using Kubernetes.

² The new name for the “Workers” presented in “D4.4 Initial implementation and report of Data and Content Curation Services” [LynxD44]

- Shared memory service: it is used by both the Workflow Manager engine and the task executors for sharing large sized objects.

Furthermore the Workflow Manager offers two APIs:

- Custom API³: it is the API offered by the Lynx system to start and manage instances of the population workflow, which is described in Section 3.2 of this document. The documentation of Workflow Manager Custom API is available in the Lynx Platform API webpage (on <https://lynx-project.eu/doc/api/>) and ANNEX 2 provides a snapshot of its documentation.
- Camunda API: it is the API provided out of the box with the Camunda engine and can be used by developers for testing and debugging.

3.2 POPULATION WORKFLOW

The population workflow is a general model for a workflow that takes as input:

- a Lynx document
- an enrichment configuration, which defines the enrichment services to be activated and the models which should be used
- a collection identifier
- an index identifier

Then, the workflow consists of the following steps:

1. Enriching the document according to the provided enrichment configuration.
2. Saving the document in the specified collection
3. Indexing it in the specified index (optional)

The BPMN realisation of the population workflow is shown in [Figure 8](#) (“LKGP”). Furthermore, more details regarding the input parameters can be found in the Lynx API webpage: <https://lynx-project.eu/doc/api/>

³ The new name for the “Pilot API” presented in “*D4.4 Initial implementation and report of Data and Content Curation Services*” [LynxD44]

Figure 8. Figure “LKG”: BPMN model for the LKG population workflow

3.3 ENRICHMENT INTERFACE

The task executors for the enrichment tasks types defined in the LKG population workflow (e.g. Translation to EN, Translation to DE, NER ...) perform their tasks by connecting to the appropriate enrichment microservices. To simplify the integration between task executors and enrichment microservices we have designed an approach composed of two REST API definitions:

- The Analysis API (Figure 9) :
 - Uses a POST method
 - Input: a RDF Lynx document⁴ and an enrichment model identifier. There are no restrictions on other possible optional parameters
 - Output: the enriched RDF Lynx document and a “non-existing model” error if the provided enrichment model does not exist
- The Models API (Figure 10):
 - Uses a GET method
 - Output: all the possible choices of enrichments models with their identifiers and, optionally, a short description for them

⁴ The latest version of the RDF Lynx document data model is described in Deliverable D2.8 [LynxD2.8]

The Analysis API is used by enrichment task executors for connecting to enrichment microservices. Furthermore, it can be used by Lynx users for enriching documents without the need of storing them in the LKG or indexing them. The Models API can be used by Lynx users to check which models are available and their purpose.

Figure 9. The Analysis API for the Temporal Extraction microservice

Figure 10. The Models API for the Named Entity Recognition microservice

By complying with this interface, an enrichment microservice can be easily added in the LKG population workflow. The idea of having a single contract has also diminished the amount of integration code that has to be tested and maintained.

3.4 CONTRACT ANALYSIS AND GEOTHERMAL PROJECT ANALYSIS WORKFLOWS

The population workflow has been designed with the aim of being sufficiently general to cover all the other ingestion and document analysis scenarios of Lynx, that are Contract Analysis and Geothermal Project Analysis. In particular:

- The Geothermal Project Analysis workflow ([Figure 11](#)) can be obtained by setting:
 - Entity linking active with model “1E260842-45A0-0001-C721-16292C0E51A0”
 - Dutch to English translation active with model “smt-2eb02c32-1406-45a0-8974-0310becf564b”
 - Indexing enabled
- The Contract Analysis ([Figure 12](#)) workflow can be obtained by setting:
 - Named Entity Recognition active with model “ner-de_ajj-wikinerTrainLOC”
 - Geographical NER active with model “ner-de_ajj-wikinerTrainLOC”
 - Temporal Extraction active with model “model-de”
 - Entity Linking active (the model vary)
 - Indexing enabled

Figure 11. Geothermal Project Analysis workflow

Figure 12. Contract Analysis workflow

The main advantage of having a single BPMN model covering all the three document analysis scenarios (“Legal Knowledge Graph Population”, “Contract Analysis” and “Geothermal Project Analysis”, because “Labour Law Analysis” is considered an information retrieval scenario) is that we have significantly decreased the efforts needed to test and maintain the three workflows.

4 CONCLUSIONS

This report provides the description of the final implementation of the Curation Workflow Manager and the Document Manager. The Curation Workflow Manager implementation described in this report is based on the intermediate description provided in “D4.4 Initial implementation and report of Data and Content Curation Services” [LynxD44].

The final implementation of the Curation Workflow Manager is based on Camunda BPMN Engine together with some self-implemented components, which allows not only the management but also the execution of workflows while the definition of new workflows is done via a graphical interface (Camunda Modeler).

The implementation of the Document Manager is not only a storage and retrieval module for documents, but it also has the functionality of storing and providing access to the linked data (Legal Knowledge Graph). It has been implemented based on Trellis LDP, and extended with some additional HTTP methods to adapt its functionality to project needs.

ANNEX 1 – IMPLEMENTATION DETAILS (CODE)

This annex contains all the repositories related to DCM and CWM.

Repository URL	Description
https://gitlab.com/superlynx/alp_wm	Workflow Manager engine
https://gitlab.com/superlynx/workers	Workers
https://gitlab.com/superlynx/workflows	Contains the implemented workflows in BPMN format.
https://gitlab.com/superlynx/dcm	Document Manager

Table 2. List of repositories related to DCM and WM.

NOTE: some of the repositories are established as private access but credentials are offered upon request.

ANNEX 2 – WORKFLOW MANAGER API

The tool <https://mrin9.github.io/RapiPdf/> was used to generate these report.

API Reference

Workflow manager

API Version: 1.0.0

The Workflow Manager is the component of the Lynx platform responsible for the execution of workflows.

Terminology

-
- Workflow: a model for a sequence of operations applied to data and data stores. Workflows are represented using Business Process Model and Notation (BPMN).
-
- Workflow instance: a runtime instance of a workflow.
-
- Population workflow: a workflow that first enriches the input RDF Lynx document according to the provided enrichment configuration, and then saves the resulting enriched document in the specified collection of a Lynx document platform. Optionally the document can also be indexed using the Sear service.
-

Execution of the population workflow

- 1.
2. Send a POST request using the /workflows/LKGP controller. The body of your request should contain a valid RDF Lynx document.
3. Wait until the workflow is completed, you can check whether it is successfully completed using the /workflows/status/{workflowInstanceId} controller. The required workflowInstanceId path parameter is provided in the response obtained in step 1.
4. Once the workflow is completed, you can verify that the document has been ingested in the Lynx platform:
 - Retrieve the enriched document using the Lynx Document Manager. The documentId is the

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one returned in step 1.

-
- Perform a search using the Lynx Search service.

CONTACT

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Security and Authentication

SECURITY SCHEMES

KEY	TYPE	DESCRIPTION
authorizationCodeLynx	oauth2, jwt	

API

1. POPULATION-WORKFLOW-RUNTIME-CONTROLLER

1.1 GET /workflows/population/processed-characters

Get the number of processed characters in given a interval of time

REQUEST

QUERY PARAMETERS

NAME	TYPE	DESCRIPTION
*tag	string	The tag of the group
*intervalStart	date-time	The start of the time interval in which processed characters are counted
*intervalEnd	date-time	The end of the time interval in which processed characters are counted

RESPONSE

STATUS CODE - 200: OK

RESPONSE MODEL - */*

integer

1.2 GET /workflows/population/tags/{tag}/instances-status

Get the status of a group of population workflow instances by tag

REQUEST

PATH PARAMETERS

NAME	TYPE	DESCRIPTION
*tag	string	The tag of the group

RESPONSE

STATUS CODE - 200: OK

RESPONSE MODEL - */*

```
{
  successfullyCompletedInstances [string]
  failedInstances [string]
  activeInstances [string]
  successfullyCompletedInstancesNumber integer
  failedInstancesNumber integer
  activeInstancesNumber integer
  totalNum integer
  completionPercentage integer
}
```

1.3 GET /workflows/population/instances/{populationWorkflowInstanceId}

Get a population workflow instance.

REQUEST

PATH PARAMETERS

NAME	TYPE	DESCRIPTION
*populationWorkflowInstanceId	string	The population workflow instance identifier

RESPONSE

STATUS CODE - 200: OK

RESPONSE MODEL - application/json

```
{
  documentPlatformId string
  documentId string
  completed boolean
  completionPercentage number
  errorList [{
    Array of object:
      errorCode string
      errorMessage string
  }]
  collectionId string
  indexId string
  tag string
  completedSuccessfully boolean
}
```

1.4 POST /workflows/population/instances

Create a new population workflow instance.

REQUEST

QUERY PARAMETERS

NAME	TYPE	DESCRIPTION
*documentPlatform	string	The document platform to be used to store and index the document ("ldp" or "upm-elastic")
*collectionId	string	The collection in which the enriched document should be added or updated. An update will take place if and only if a lynx document with the specified URI already exists.
indexId	string	The index in which the enriched document should be added or updated. An update will take place if and only if a lynx document with the specified URI already exists.
entityLinkingProjectId	string	The thesaurus to be used by the Entity Linking service. If not set the linking of entities will be deactivated.
enTranslationModelId	string	The translation model to be used for the en translation. If not set the translation to en will be deactivated.

NAME	TYPE	DESCRIPTION
esTranslationModelId	string	The translation model to be used for the es translation. If not set the translation to es will be deactivated.
neTranslationModelId	string	The translation model to be used for the ne translation. If not set the translation to ne will be deactivated.
deTranslationModelId	string	The translation model to be used for the de translation. If not set the translation to de will be deactivated.
NERModelId	string	The NER model. If not set NER will be deactivated.
GEOModelId	string	The GEO model. If not set GEO will be deactivated.
TimExModelId	string	The TimEx model. If not set TimEx will be deactivated.
SummModelId	string	The summarization model. If not set Summ will be deactivated.
priority	int64	The priority of the workflow instance. To greater values corresponds higher priority
tag	string	A tag for the workflow. Tags can be used later to query for the status of tagged groups of workflow instances. If not set the workflow instance will be tagged with the "default" string.

REQUEST BODY - application/ld+json
string

RESPONSE

STATUS CODE - 202: The population workflow instance has been created.

RESPONSE MODEL - application/json

```
{
  workflowInstanceId string
  documentId         string
  collectionId       string
  documentPlatformId string
  indexId            string
}
```

STATUS CODE - 400: The input document is not a Lynx document.

RESPONSE MODEL - text/plain

1.5 DELETE /workflows/population/instances

Delete population workflow instances based on their tag.

REQUEST

QUERY PARAMETERS

NAME	TYPE	DESCRIPTION
tag	string	The tag of the instances to be deleted

RESPONSE

STATUS CODE - 200: OK

RESPONSE MODEL - application/json

```
{
  links [{
    Array of object:
      method string
      href string
      rel string
    }]
  id string
  definitionId string
  businessKey string
  caseInstanceId string
  ended boolean
  suspended boolean
  tenantId string
}
```

1.6 GET /workflows/population/processed-characters-by-service

Get the number of processed characters in given a interval of time for each enrichment model

REQUEST

QUERY PARAMETERS

NAME	TYPE	DESCRIPTION
*tag	string	The tag of the group
*intervalStart	date-time	The start of the time interval in which processed characters are counted
*intervalEnd	date-time	The end of the time interval in which processed characters are counted

RESPONSE

STATUS CODE - 200: OK

RESPONSE MODEL - */*

```
{
}
```

1.7 GET /workflows/population/tags

Get the existing tags

REQUEST

No request parameters

RESPONSE

STATUS CODE - 200: OK

RESPONSE MODEL - */*

[string]

ANNEX 3 – DOCUMENT MANAGER API

The tool <https://mrin9.github.io/RapiPdf/> was used to generate these report.

API Reference

Document Manager REST API

API Version: 1.0

Common endpoints for creating, reading and deleting collections, documents and annotations.

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Security and Authentication

SECURITY SCHEMES

KEY	TYPE	DESCRIPTION
authorizationCodeLynx	oauth2, jwt	

API

1. ANNOTATIONS

1.1 GET /collections/{collectionId}/documents/{documentId}/annotations

Gets all the annotations of a document

Returns a complete representation of the annotations of the document

REQUEST

PATH PARAMETERS

NAME	TYPE	DESCRIPTION
*collectionId	string	
*documentId	string	

RESPONSE

STATUS CODE - 200: OK

RESPONSE MODEL - application/json

string

RESPONSE MODEL - application/rdf+xml

string

RESPONSE MODEL - text/turtle

string

RESPONSE MODEL - application/n-triples

string

RESPONSE MODEL - application/ld+json

string

1.2 PUT /collections/{collectionId}/documents/{documentId}/annotations

Updates annotations of a document

This will replace all previous annotations of the document. The request body should be a valid NIF 2.1 document

REQUEST

PATH PARAMETERS

NAME	TYPE	DESCRIPTION
*collectionId	string	
*documentId	string	

REQUEST BODY - application/rdf+xml

string

RESPONSE

STATUS CODE - 204: No Content

1.3 POST /collections/{collectionId}/documents/{documentId}/annotations

Creates new annotation(s)

The request body should be a valid NIF 2.1 document

REQUEST

PATH PARAMETERS

NAME	TYPE	DESCRIPTION
*collectionId	string	
*documentId	string	

REQUEST BODY - application/rdf+xml

string

This string should be a valid NIF 2.0 turtle

RESPONSE

STATUS CODE - 201: Created

RESPONSE MODEL - */*

boolean

1.4 GET /collections/{collectionId}/documents/{documentId}/annotations/**

Gets an annotation

This will show a specific annotation of a document.

REQUEST

PATH PARAMETERS

NAME	TYPE	DESCRIPTION
*collectionId	string	
*documentId	string	

RESPONSE

STATUS CODE - 200: OK

RESPONSE MODEL - application/json

string

RESPONSE MODEL - application/rdf+xml

string

RESPONSE MODEL - text/turtle

string

RESPONSE MODEL - application/n-triples

string

RESPONSE MODEL - application/ld+json

string

1.5 DELETE /collections/{collectionId}/documents/{documentId}/ annotations/**

Deletes an existing annotation

Deletes an annotation

REQUEST

PATH PARAMETERS

NAME	TYPE	DESCRIPTION
*collectionId	string	
*documentId	string	

RESPONSE

STATUS CODE - 200: OK

1.6 GET /collections/{collectionId}/documents/{documentId}/ annotations/ list

Lists all the annotations of a document

Returns an array of annotation identifiers.

REQUEST

PATH PARAMETERS

NAME	TYPE	DESCRIPTION
*collectionId	string	
*documentId	string	

RESPONSE

STATUS CODE - 200: OK

RESPONSE MODEL - application/json

string

2. COLLECTIONS

2.1 POST /collections/{collectionId}

Creates a new collection

any slug with no empty spaces

REQUEST

PATH PARAMETERS

NAME	TYPE	DESCRIPTION
*collectionId	string	

RESPONSE

STATUS CODE - 201: Created

RESPONSE MODEL - */*

boolean

2.2 DELETE /collections/{collectionId}

Deletes an existing collection

the collection must be empty

REQUEST

PATH PARAMETERS

NAME	TYPE	DESCRIPTION
*collectionId	string	

RESPONSE

STATUS CODE - 202: Accepted

RESPONSE MODEL - */*

string

2.3 GET /collections

Lists the available collections

REQUEST

No request parameters

RESPONSE

STATUS CODE - 200: OK

RESPONSE MODEL - */*

string

3. DOCUMENTS

3.1 GET /collections/{collectionId}/documents/{documentId}

Retrieves an existing document

The document has not annotations, in principle

REQUEST

PATH PARAMETERS

NAME	TYPE	DESCRIPTION
*collectionId	string	
*documentId	string	

RESPONSE

STATUS CODE - 200: OK

RESPONSE MODEL - application/json

string

RESPONSE MODEL - application/rdf+xml

string

RESPONSE MODEL - application/ld+json

string

RESPONSE MODEL - text/turtle

string

RESPONSE MODEL - text/plain

string

3.2 DELETE /collections/{collectionId}/documents/{documentId}

Deletes an existing document

REQUEST

PATH PARAMETERS

NAME	TYPE	DESCRIPTION
*collectionId	string	
*documentId	string	

RESPONSE

STATUS CODE - 200: OK

3.3 GET /collections/{collectionId}/documents/search

Makes a search

REQUEST

PATH PARAMETERS

NAME	TYPE	DESCRIPTION
*collectionId	string	

QUERY PARAMETERS

NAME	TYPE	DESCRIPTION
query	array of string	
limit	int32	
offset	int32	

RESPONSE

STATUS CODE - 200: OK

RESPONSE MODEL - application/json

```
{
  total      integer
  docs [{
    Array of object:
    @context  string
    id        string
    type      [string]
    text      string
    metadata {
    }
    parts [{
      Array of object:
      id      string
      type    [string]
      metadata {
      }
      offset_ini  integer
      offset_end  integer
      title {
        empty  boolean
      }
      parent      string
      referenceContext string
    }
  ]
  annotations [{
    Array of object:
    id      string
    type    [string]
    source  string
    referenceContext string
    offset_ini  integer
    offset_end  integer
    anchorOf   string
    comment    string
    annotationUnit [{

```

```

Array of object:
  id    string
  type  [string]
}]
}]
offset_ini    integer
offset_end    integer
translations {
}
}]
}
    
```

3.4 GET /collections/{collectionId}/documents

List documents.

Retrieves a list of all documents in a collection

REQUEST

PATH PARAMETERS

NAME	TYPE	DESCRIPTION
*collectionId	string	

QUERY PARAMETERS

NAME	TYPE	DESCRIPTION
sort	string	
limit	int32	
offset	int32	

RESPONSE

STATUS CODE - 200: OK

RESPONSE MODEL - application/json

```

{
  total    integer
  docs [{
    Array of object:
    @context    string
    id          string
    type        [string]
    text        string
    metadata {
    }
    parts [{
    Array of object:
    id          string
    type        [string]
    metadata {
    }
    offset_ini  integer
    offset_end  integer
    }
    }
  }
    
```

```

    title {
      empty boolean
    }
    parent      string
    referenceContext string
  }]
  annotations [{
    Array of object:
    id          string
    type        [string]
    source      string
    referenceContext string
    offset_ini  integer
    offset_end  integer
    anchorOf    string
    comment     string
    annotationUnit [{
      Array of object:
      id  string
      type [string]
    }]
  }]
  offset_ini  integer
  offset_end  integer
  translations {
  }
  }]
}

```

3.5 PUT /collections/{collectionId}/documents

Updates a document

This will update a document. The previous version of the document will be overwritten and the the annotations re-evaluated

REQUEST

PATH PARAMETERS

NAME	TYPE	DESCRIPTION
*collectionId	string	

REQUEST BODY - application/json

string

REQUEST BODY - application/rdf+xml

string

REQUEST BODY - application/ld+json

string

RESPONSE

STATUS CODE - 204: No Content

RESPONSE MODEL - */*

string

3.6 POST /collections/{collectionId}/documents

Creates a new document

IDs are kept in the case of RDF input. When input is application/json, then the DM will create a new ID.

REQUEST

PATH PARAMETERS

NAME	TYPE	DESCRIPTION
*collectionId	string	

REQUEST BODY - application/json

string

REQUEST BODY - application/rdf+xml

string

REQUEST BODY - application/ld+json

string

RESPONSE

STATUS CODE - 201: Created

RESPONSE MODEL - */*

string

4. VALIDATE

Validation of documents

4.1 POST /validate/

Validates a document

Determines whether a LynxDocument is valid against a series of rules or not.

REQUEST

REQUEST BODY - application/rdf+xml

string

REQUEST BODY - application/ld+json

string

RESPONSE

STATUS CODE - 200: OK

RESPONSE MODEL - */*

string

5. VERSION-CONTROLLER

5.1 GET /version/

REQUEST

QUERY PARAMETERS

NAME	TYPE	DESCRIPTION
value	string	

RESPONSE

STATUS CODE - 200: OK

RESPONSE MODEL - */*

string

REFERENCES

- [LynxD11] Jorge González-Conejero, Emma Teodoro, & Pompeu Casanovas. (2018). Lynx D1.1 Functional Requirements Analysis Report. <https://zenodo.org/record/1256836>
- [LynxD24] Víctor Rodríguez-Doncel; Socorro Bernardos; Rebeca Varela; Patricia Martín. (2018). Lynx D2.4 Data Management Plan. <https://zenodo.org/record/3236320>
- [LynxD39] Maria Khvalchik, Artem Revenko, Christian Sageder, Víctor Rodríguez-Doncel and Pablo Calleja-Ibáñez. D3.9 Information Retrieval and Recommender Services. <https://zenodo.org/record/3870457>
- [LynxD41] Julián Moreno-Schneider, & Georg Rehm. (2018). D4.1 Pilots Requirements Analysis Report. <https://zenodo.org/record/3236427>
- [LynxD42] Julián Moreno-Schneider, & Georg Rehm. (2018). D4.2 Intermediate version of Workflow definition. <https://zenodo.org/record/1745324>
- [LynxD43] Julián Moreno-Schneider, & Georg Rehm. (2019). D4.3 Final version of Workflow definition. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3235767>
- [LynxD44] Julián Moreno-Schneider, & Georg Rehm. (2019). D4.4 Initial implementation and report of Data and Content Curation Services. <https://zenodo.org/record/3557757>
- [Bourgonje2016] Peter Bourgonje, Julián Moreno Schneider, Georg Rehm, and Felix Sasaki. Processing Document Collections to Automatically Extract Linked Data: Semantic Storytelling Technologies for Smart Curation Workflows. In Aldo Gangemi and Claire Gardent, editors, *Proceedings of the 2nd International Workshop on Natural Language Generation and the Semantic Web (WebNLG 2016)*, pages 13-16, Edinburgh, UK, 9 2016. The Association for Computational Linguistics.
- [MorenoSchneider2018a] Julian Moreno Schneider and Georg Rehm. Towards a Workflow Manager for Curation Technologies in the Legal Domain. In Georg Rehm, Víctor Rodríguez-Doncel, and Julian Moreno Schneider, editors, *Proceedings of the LREC 2018 Workshop on Language Resources and Technologies for the Legal Knowledge Graph*, pages 30-35, Miyazaki, Japan, 5 2018. 12 May 2018.
- [MorenoSchneider2018b] Julian Moreno Schneider and Georg Rehm. Curation Technologies for the Construction and Utilisation of Legal Knowledge Graphs. In Georg Rehm, Víctor Rodríguez-Doncel, and Julian Moreno Schneider, editors, *Proceedings of the LREC 2018 Workshop on Language Resources and Technologies for the Legal Knowledge Graph*, pages 23-29, Miyazaki, Japan, 5 2018. 12 May 2018.